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Basic formulations for treatment of chronic human disease.

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We describe four basic formulations for treatment of chronic human disease using transcriptome data from cells or tissues of affected patients and healthy controls to determine differential expression. In the first, only cytokines and chemokines dysregulated in expression and up-regulated are targeted to resolve inflammation and facilitate regeneration and wound healing locally. In the second, a kinase and phosphatase pair are chosen for small molecule inhibition. In the third formulation, a single chemokine is targeted in conjunction with a kinase/phosphatase pair as well as a selected target of interest. In chronic diseases where symptomology and differential expression suggest allergic components to disease pathology, genes with neuroactive functions or genes with functions in mast cell biology are chosen as the selected target. In the fourth formulation, genes with functions in the inflammatory response from the Cox (cyclooxygenase), Alox (arachidonate lipoxygenase), and prostaglandin families that are essential components of a disease gene signature are targeted for joint small molecule inhibition.